

OPPORTUNITIES FOR THE USE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN THE PROCESS OF TECHNOLOGICAL EDUCATION

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ANNOTATION

This article education system in information technologies, the use of scientific-pedagogical issues, computer, telecommunications, applied experience, learning in the process of information technology in use students only on the screen information to see and them to accept not, but they themselves also this process of creative participation of the issues illuminated.

Key words: educational process, educational technology, information technology, education system, personality development, information culture, computer literacy, education, reliability, multimedia tools

Introduction

Our country future, its development, world community in the role, obviously, who is an adult, perfect young generation of fate with associated. Independence of the initial years of the education system reform to the issue of state policy at the level of attention being the focus, the young generation of the world standards corresponding in the conditions of knowledge would take, mature human being in formation of, abilities and aptitude of the occurrence, production, the main purpose is to be defined is

Twenty-first century, computer technology, advanced pedagogical and information technologies (the internet), high thinking, science and technique of the table to the development of the age of is. XXI century the beginning of come, "Electronic education", "E-governance", "Open education", "Distance education", "Informed education" such as concepts in our life day to day integrated into has been

New technology, electronic services in our daily life an integral part has become. Society information- have technology is increasingly more dependent is the fact that in regard, these technologies protect to and of them use the national interest for the solution of the significance it has.

Information technology in educational process to be added - this high professional education system modernization for the necessary condition. In recent years, Internet technology rapid development, it is observed, that while learning in the process the internet using new methods to work out the current to the need of causing out of being, their goal is not only learning the effectiveness of the increase, but also, students of professional, information and intellectual competence formation for the conditions you create. Education methods use information technologies in the application of the reader, students to science, relevant sources for use in the interest of the increase to the data, open access, education activities of entities of the network with the mutual relations of the organization to less time spending and comes.

Literature analysis

Scientists Have T.S. The pan and L.N.Vavilov in interactive teaching methods to practical problems solution in your knowledge to realize, mastering and creative application process boost to returns. Efficiency students not only knowledge you get, but also from right-the right of use of the process in more active involvement to through ensures that the overall results and the effects distinguish. Training in computer networks technology by using the training sessions of the organization to and the lessons suggestions work out. Lessons in classrooms the students the necessary knowledge and skills to be able to be for the computer in the classroom, the organization of local from the network I have used the case in a clear and quick, able to be. Local network running the computer in class, conducted training sessions to the students the lesson on the topic of on given instructions apart, other programs from ineffective use the way that it does not pour. The subject related information in the web server program is installed in the computer data base to be taken, the education of the institutions internal network through contact be and the network through the new information and take can.

The main part

Education process into the development of a look if you throw it, today's the day the computer of telecommunication with the help of how important pedagogical issues solutions confidence to ensure we can. Education in various fields of computer and telecommunications of being applied from experience that seeing as you can, information technology us a number of positive opportunities to create does not give any, of the following, all it may include:

- professor-teachers, academic staff and students all the different types of cooperation in scientific research (each different scientific-practical projects using genuine creative research, independent practical activities, independent knowledge gain, practical creative activities and other types of partner) of the organization to;
- scientific-methodical center of education, bearing the broad masses of quick expert advice, up to and delivery;
- remote units education and pedagogical personnel of the skills increase network nest up to;
- operational information exchange;
- education partners, this student, the ones who were, be, scientific personnel to from of look, them thoughts sharing the form to, treated culture and mind-review of quick, and clearly express to ;
- cultural, ethnic, wide comprehensive positive information with thoughts sharing as a result of the age of cultural and social ability , and the disabled and so on.

Tech education in the process of information technology methodology in students only screen information browsing and them accept not, but their of also this process of creative involved are we should. Education didactic texture with paired hidden opportunities in the world of direct computer communication with connected to this education in the field of modern and promising goals has.

Didactic function as we study-educational process, in particular an order applied by the educational means of the external texture of the apparent , we understand. This is their training process to use functions, in keeping with the place and importance is.

Next year integration (reciprocal link without scientific-pedagogical cooperation, creative environment to create) the idea of rapid developing of theoretical and practical

studies of the basis for been has. Integration one on the hand of education to the recipient, "the world is familiar" select and sciences scientific basics to know if you teach, second hand education of time to decide on the outcome of the case , it leisure time to productive use , it teaches. This is the reason for education in the process many of the issues and their solutions of the students thinking activity to grow at should be. Those same aspects are more effective to achieve to the subjective factor, for example, the education of the recipient variation, interest, demand, intellectual development is very skillful use to know required are.

This is in achieving our teachers very also hand in hand that come with educational technologies, one of many methods there are. Those projects are one of them that method. The method of the project exactly to the activities of the partnership , it gives a very good effect to apply. Also in scientific circles, scientific-methodical seminar, independent education in the organization of joint creative in creating an environment can be used effectively. Them more meaningful and inclusive education of the debtors future research activities on the ground in the creation of computer, telecommunications and information technology overestimate the importance of.

In this process, the computer communication and information technology for the efficient use of the pedagogical goals of the stress let's take. Be applied modern information technologies in education – this world education is important in the development process and is one of the priority areas.

Come to the present day, almost all of the education process in the republic of joints in the field of computer engineering and information science and the effective use of technology tools has been established. Information has penetrated deep into the process of education. Information and communication technologies educational technologies based on new learning, speeding up the process, increase the pace, extensive knowledge of the warehouse and to receive information from this deep knowledge allows learning and mastering. As it is known to us, information technologies in education – this information prepare and education techniques and computer software to the recipient, it is the process of using signals.

Information technology in education use in the educational process, check out the two involved in the transmission of information available component: hardware (computer engineering , and communication tools) and software created for different purposes. Lesson preparation and lesson productive in the process from a computer component this functional options for the use of teachers and also to check out the terms of use and should be very good because you know too technical features and specific software able to influence the educational process.

It understand to the lesson in the process of computer technique, what to methodology is lab and information technology tools using how methodological issues is charged, that the question to answer we need.

The information in the following technologies use pedagogical goals:

- ✓ personally development(thought;
- ✓ aesthetic education;
- ✓ to develop research activities;
- ✓ formation of information culture;
- ✓ the preparation of professionals in a certain industry in the user's general information and preparation ("computer literacy")consisting of the social order and fulfill;

✓ educational-educational process productivity, quality of education and to increase the effectiveness, learn to know the important business aspects that provide integration of information and science at the expense of the subject associated deepening of bilateral relations.

The methodological tools of information technology options are the following:

- knowledge visualization;
- and decide on the outcome of education;
- the development of objects, drawings, and images of the construction, the operation (in a computer) shows sequences of the consummation of the process of track options;
- objects, the modeling of processes and phenomena;
- establishment and operation of the data base;
- using multimedia tools and interesting in the form of access to the resource described the large amounts of information to know;
- when working with the computer directory and information search, processing, and sending skills formation;
- his self-control to know;
- exercise strengthening study and independently prepared;
- increase the reliability of education (different games,
- to find the optimal solution in complex situations, skills formation;
- see the development of a certain of thinking (e.g., visual, model);
- the formation of the culture of educational activities; information culture formation;
- students have independent work time and time allocation to know to teach and so on.

Now to the second of the above component, that is, pedagogical drew attention to the type of software. Education in information technology in technical means of the application process check out a number of special software are also used. In the educational process - oriented software – the sphere of their studying this over any science is composed of software, thus the study of the field of science technology and educational activities associated with the implementation of the terms of different provides. Different types of the educational process and functionality of such software is called software tools that provide pedagogical. Different types of educational software currently and there are groups. Depending on the task of teaching the following pedagogical software consists of:

textbooks (classes); exercise (tutor) programs; supervisory programs (shell test); information- (encyclopedia) programs;
imitation programs;
show the programs (slides, video);
educational-game programs;
to conduct meaningful leisure time focused programs (pc games: fun games, strategy games, management games, logical games, sports games, etc.).

Thus, the computer communication and information technologies will remain in the memory for a long time and is obtained by using the knowledge to apply them in practice within a short period of time, with a repeat later you can restore it.

Tech the in the process of technologies, i.e., the function of the activity of the computer as a tool of the teacher's use, registration of the facts clearly, large amounts of data storage and transmission, and re data-statistical work is based on the real opportunities to reflect.

Conclusion

In this lesson, the teacher education process management to optimize the effectiveness of the educational process and increase, information relevant to the subject at the same time, distribute, parameters to with educational work (information search, analysis, selection), work with the team influences make up the teachers time to read from a distance in the process of saving.

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